

An Assessment of Collaboration Competencies as a Correlate for the Career Development of Workers with Hearing Impairment in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed Collaboration Competencies as a Correlate for the Career Development of Workers with Hearing Impairment in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon. Specifically, the study examined the extent to which certain indicators of collaboration competencies such as; the ability to understand others, participatory ability, collaborative problem solving ability, team spirit and the ability to be tolerant can influence the career development of workers with hearing impairment in Fako Division South West Region of Cameroon. To achieve this, a case study research design was used and the sample of a sample of 39 persons were selected across the seven Sub-Divisions of Fako. 15 workers with hearing impairment and 24 of their colleagues, made up the sample of the study. The sample emerged through the use of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. An interview guide and a focus group discussion guide were used for data collection. Interview and focus group discussion guides were analysed using the process of thematic analysis, whereby concepts or ideas were grouped under umbrella terms of key words with the support of Atlas Ti 5.2 (Atlas Ti GMBH 2006). The findings revealed that collaboration competencies play an important role to improve on the career development of workers with hearing impairment, by developing certain positive qualities in them such as; flexibility, sociable, creativity, enjoy working together, collaborative working relationship, tolerant, demonstrative behaviour, the ability to understand others, the ability to be patient, to be empathetic, to be curious, the ability to manage change and the ability to understand oneself. These positive qualities of collaboration competencies possess by workers with hearing impairment, improves on their career development, by helping them to develop a collaborative working relationship, develop a competitive spirit, work very hard, be duty conscious, be job focused, job effective, gain environmental motivation, encourages them to learn from others, retain their job, be patients, develop new skills and to develop self-pride.

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KEYWORDS: Collaboration Competencies, Career Development and Workers with hearing impairment

1. INTRODUCTION

The wish of every individual as he or she grows older in life is to have a career from which he can be financially independent, socially comfortable, productive in the society and have a sense of self-respect. But living in an age of innovation, digitalization and globalization, to decide which career path to follow and coping within this career path has become a very huge challenge to each one of us. With the introduction of modern technology, which has brought about great advancements, growth, expansion, and a shift in the job market during this period of 4th Industrial Revolution, there is a shift from linear and traditional career path to more protein career as people want more career mobility (Aziz, 2019).

With the above intricacy in place, choosing the right career, or simple know what it might be is not easy, even for highly

skilled individuals. Doing so is even more difficult for those who lack adequate training or face special challenges such as disabilities (Levinson and Palmer, 2005). Persons with hearing impairment being one of the categories of persons with disability, therefore face similar challenges in their career development path. Though these persons possess special skills and capabilities suited for major industries, the job pursuit and the career development process is very challenging for them (BoldLimited, 2019). Expanding on the above, Heibutzki (2020) stated that, within the work environment, workers with hearing impairment face challenges such as: the application challenges, discriminatory practices, employer misconceptions, isolation at work and lack of empathy from potential employers who don't want to treat them as equals. These sometimes leave

workers with hearing impairment ostracized by their co-workers and vulnerable to poor job evaluations.

In Cameroon, just like many African countries, De Clerck in Ray, Wallace, Mbuagbaw and Cocburn (2017) revealed that, persons with hearing impairment experience very low quality of life. She reiterated that, the societal attitudes towards this group of persons is highly discriminatory and questioned their ability to participate in activities associated with 'full personhood' such as employment, marriage, having children and supporting a family. To intricate on their employment, De Clerck postulated that, the career opportunities for persons with hearing impairment are restricted and for those who manage to obtain a career, the situation is often difficult and precarious, leading to high rate of joblessness, financial barriers and further marginalization, which negatively expose this class of persons to a state of self-doubt and bitter experiences of human rights violations such as sexual abuse as they come beggars in the community.

Underscoring the above, Fox (2010) opined that, one population in the city of Buea and Cameroon in general which continues to be unjustifiably under-represented is that of the 'Deaf' community (persons with hearing impairment), as the challenges of regular employment opportunities leave them in a state of further relegation and poverty with very limited opportunities to become contributors to the Cameroonian society. In order to assist workers with hearing impairment develop in their career, this study sets out to investigate the concept of Collaboration Competencies as a Correlate for Career Development of Workers with Hearing Impairment in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon.

2. Literature Review

The two major concepts to be reviewed are, the concept of collaboration competencies and career development.

2.1. The Concept of Collaboration Competencies

Collaboration competencies has to do with the ability to learn from others, to understand and respect the needs, perspectives and actions of others (empathy), to understand, relate to and be sensitive to others, to deal with conflicts in a group and to facilitate collaborative and participatory problem solving (Haan, 2010; Rieckmann, 2012; Wiek et al., 2011) in (UNESCO, 2017). According Doyle (2018), collaboration is essential in almost all aspects of life and work. Nearly every imaginable job today entails at least some joint effort by members of a team to work together collaboratively. This makes collaboration an essential skill in most sectors of the work world. He further explained that, collaboration competencies enable workers to interface productively with other colleagues. Successful collaboration requires a cooperative spirit and mutual respect. Doyle extended that, collaboration can take various forms, including between bosses and subordinates. Service providers can collaborate with clients to achieve goals, and vendors can cooperate with customers to produce products or services. Collaboration can also take place between individuals outside one's realm of employment including business partners, customers, clients, contractors, volunteers and suppliers.

Keast & Mandell (2013), gave core collaboration competencies/capabilities and characteristics, some of

which are; the ability to read interactions and exchanges, to be trustworthy, have a sense of humour, have empathy (step in shoes), be flexible, be patience, perseverance, commitment, have a cooperative spirit, have strategic relationship building skills, group process skills, change management skills, negotiation skills and many others.

Adding to the above, Rise (2018) grouped the components of collaborative competencies into six main heading of what a good collaborator should have namely; communication, authenticity, compromise, tolerance, team player and reliability. Tallying to the above, Keast & Mandell (2013) expressed that, collaboration competencies involves the ability to mobilise and energise others to create a common vision towards problem solving. Collaboration encompasses the ability to facilitate the work of others, read a situation as it unfolds and be instinctively resourceful by identifying and tapping into the range of assets held by members. Successful collaborators listen and take time to learn about the problem before launching into solutions. In so doing, they 'step into others' shoes' and try to appreciate the various perspectives and experiences of members.

Although collaboration competencies is often described as a "soft skill," in today's workplace, it is just as vital as hard skills such as one's educational background and/or technical knowledge. And even though productive collaboration skills may not be innate to some individuals, they can easily be acquired through learning and practise. Some aspects of collaboration competencies of interest in this study are; the ability to understand others, participatory ability, collaborative problem solving ability, team player and the ability to be tolerant.

2.2. The Concept of Career Development

Career development is the lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure, and transitions in order to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future. According to MBASKool (2020), career development is the series of activities or the on-going/lifelong process of developing one's career. Career development usually refers to managing one's career in an intra-organizational or inter-organizational scenario. It involves training on new skills, moving to higher job responsibilities, making a career change within the same organization, moving to a different organization or starting one's own business. Characterising the above, Daryanto (2014), career development involves employees to relate their efforts and the world of their work in fashioning their individual work identity. He added that, different aspects of career development include: (1) skills development; (2) the development of career maturity; (3) the sufficient knowledge of the individuals on their job; (4) the employees' expectation on their career development, and; (5) emotional responses, and; (6) the relevancy between employees' job, knowledge and skills with their existing career development.

Adding to the above, Mohamed (2017) explained that, career development is the interaction of psychological, sociological, economical, physical and chance factors that shape sequence of jobs, occupations/profession or career that a person may engage in throughout a lifetime. It involves a person's past, present, and future works roles and it is linked with a person's family life, self-concept, and all aspect of the person's environmental and cultural condition.

3. Research Objective

The main research objective was to investigate "Collaboration Competencies as a Correlate for Career Development of Workers with Hearing Impairment in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon"

4. Methodology

To achieve the above objective, this study employed a qualitative research method with a case study research design in order to get an in-depth or detailed understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. This research design helped the researcher to adopt ideas and produce novel propositions which could be used for later testing. Adding to the above, the case study research design was more flexible and allowed the researcher to probe or make enquiries into what the respondents were saying as the research progressed. Finally, a case study research design was used to explore and describe the phenomenon under investigation.

5. Sampling Technique and Sample

A purposive and snowball sampling techniques were used to select 15 persons with hearing impairment from the

accessible population, whose location could be reached by the researcher, with the help of the South West Regional Delegation of Social Affairs, some members in the community and some persons with hearing impairment themselves. During the sampling process, it was ensured that, those workers with hearing impairment sampled, could use the formal sign language and most have being working for at least four years.

Considering that, in a study of this nature, it is important to use every opportunity to get a very rich information on the study, it was recognized that, those who have being working with these persons with hearing impairment for at least four years, may have some contributions to make on the impact of collaboration competencies on the career development of workers with Hearing Impairment in Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon.

In that light, using a purposive and snowball sampling techniques, 24 colleagues of the workers with hearing impairment in Fako Division, South West Region were also selected and added to the 15 persons with hearing impairment sampled above making a total of 39 persons.

Table 1: Description of the Sampled Population

Sex	Workers with Hearing Impairment	Profession	Colleagues	Total
Male	2	Teachers	6	25
	2	Dress Maker	1	
	2	Carpenter	4	
	1	Fisher Man	5	
	1	Business Man	1	
Female	2	Seamstress	2	14
	4	Hair Dresser	5	
	1	Business Woman	0	
Total	15		24	39

Findings revealed that, 25 persons in the sampled population are male and 14 are female. Making it a percentage of 64.1% male and 35.9% female.

Source: South West Regional Delegation of Social Affairs Buea in collaboration with some persons with hearing impairment and some members in the community

6. Research Instruments

Research instruments are measurement tools designed to obtain data on a topic of interest from research respondents. The research instruments used for data collection in this study were an interview guide for fifteen persons with hearing impairment and a focus group discussion guide for 24 of their colleagues, together with whom made up the sample of the study. The instruments were structured to find out if the workers with hearing impairment possess collaboration competencies, and then to find out the influences of collaboration competencies on the career development of workers with hearing impairment.

7. Procedure for Data Analysis

In this study, qualitative data were collected and analysed. This allowed the researcher to elaborate on the findings in greater depth and provided a richer understanding of the data (Creswell, 2009) in (Shey, 2013). As a result, the interview guide and focus group guide were analysed

separately, using the process of thematic analysis whereby concepts or ideas were grouped under umbrella terms or key words in the context of this study.

The first stage involved deciding on the level of analysis. At this level, single words, clauses and sets of words or phrases were coded. The researcher did not initially decide on the number of concepts to code and for this reason, a pre-defined or interactive set of concept categories was not initially developed and concepts or umbrella terms were emerged from the data. To be more specific, the researcher did not have an initial code list earlier developed based on the major indicators of the study and umbrella terms or codes were generated following the standard process of thematic analysis. The primary documents of textual data were coded for existence and for frequency of concepts by coding for every independent idea as it emerged from the data.

During the coding, it was assumed that any idea that emerged at least ones was relevant. The existence of ideas was therefore considered more important than frequency or grounding. However, the frequency or grounding also reflected how many times a concept emerged and was a major indicator for emphasis, which term positivism in applied statistics.

8. Presentation of Findings

How does collaboration competencies influence the career development of persons with hearing impairment in Fako Division, South West Region Cameroon?

A. How workers with hearing impairment feel working together with others?

In stating how persons with hearing impairment feel working with others, they demonstrated aspects of "Deaf Culture", whereby they identify themselves and feel more comfortable when interacting with someone who also have a hearing impairment. This can be seen in the following expressions; *"I feel very comfortable relating with the deaf population"* *"But sometimes, when working together with the hearing population, they talk a lot behind your back."* Adding to the above, they also see themselves as victims of gossip. That is, having the feeling that others are gossiping about them *"But sometimes, when working together with the hearing population, they talk a lot behind your back"* *"they talk a lot, because I cannot hear them"*

The above notwithstanding, workers with hearing impairment expressed aspects of collaboration competencies such as being flexible, sociable and enjoy working together with others as seen in these quotations *"I do not have a problem working with others; on my part I try to relate with others"* *"I do not really have a problem with others being by my side"* *"I do not have a problem working together with people"* *"I am okay with the presence of others around me"* *In general, I feel comfortable working with others. The presence of others in the work place help me work better because sometimes I face the problem of isolation. So, if I have others around me, I am comfortable, happy and encouraged to work better."* *"In our work, you need to work with others, so I enjoy working with people"*

B. How does the ability to cooperate with others influences the performance of workers with hearing impairment?

Findings publicised that, workers with hearing impairment ability to cooperate with others, help them to develop a collaborative working relationship with others and freely learn from their colleagues as cited by them as follows: *"When people do wrong things, I help them, we learn from each other"*. *"We share knowledge on what we know, when working together"*. *"We help each other, weaker persons learn from others."* They also expressed that, cooperating with others also make me develop a competitive spirit and to work very hard as seen in this quotations *"I want to work hard in order not to be challenged in the presence of others."* *"When working with others, I do not want to be the last, so I work very hard."*

C. What workers with hearing impairment do, in order to understand others?

The reacting to the above, the study depicted that, to understand others, workers with hearing impairment, work collaboratively with others, ask a lot of questions as appreciated in these quotations; *"I am comfortable and I work seriously with others, we work as a team, we work as a chain, others help me, we exchange ideas"* *"It is generally not easy, because some workers talk a lot, but I cooperate for us to work together"* *"I ask questions to understand them"*. *"To understand how others feel, I ask a lot of questions from them."* *"You can only understand people when you get*

information from them." *"I learn to understand others by asking questions from them."* *"I get information from them on their own feelings."* *"I learn how to tolerate others, even though I face some challenges when working with others, but I am happy because I will always have people to help me at work"*

To achieve the above, they try to be tolerant as they quoted: *"Managing the emotions of others is generally not easy sometimes. People May sometime talk or behave towards you as if they are talking to children but most often I keep my calm"*. *"I try not to be angry when others are angry"* *"But I hold back my anger because they are my customers and I need their money to grow in life and feet myself"*. *"Because I do not behave like them, they still come back next time and I can keep my job"* *"Customers can really behave poorly sometimes, but I try not to be angry. Sometime I ignore when they are insulting me."*

D. How does understanding others, influence the desire to search for new knowledge at work for workers with hearing impairment?

The study revealed that, the ability to understand others, helped workers with hearing impairment to be duty conscious, that is the ability of doing one's work well, seriously and at the right time, as quoted by them *"Containing others emotions will help me work better"* *"I feel comfortable to go to work every day because I can tolerate others."*

They further explained that, understanding others, help them to be job focused, job effective and gain environmental motivation as expressed by in the following quotations; *"I ignore bad behaviour, I let go when angry with others and stay focused"* *"when you understand other people, you feel comfortable around them and so you stay focused in your work"* *"Working in a situation where majority of the population do not understand you is not easy, but I try my best to manage the situation and this help me to work very well with them."* *"Because I ignore when people talking to me poorly, I can work effectively with them"* *"Hair dressing is something you must work with others. So I manage myself to understand others in order that we work very well."* *"Managing the emotions of others help me retain my job in the sense that, I can easily relate with them at work and have the motivation to go to work every day"* *"When I relate better with my customers, I get a better understanding of the environment, so I work better"* *"when I understand my colleagues, I learn about the working environment from them better."*

E. How workers with hearing impairment collaborate to solve problems when working with others?

Findings revealed that, to collaboratively solve problems, workers with hearing impairment, do a lot of demonstration to pass out their information to others as seen in these quotations: *"It is not easy, but I use drawings and actions for us to understand each other."* They develop a collaborative working relationship and improve on their problem solving ability as seen in these quotations *"I try to share by working together with others and can also freely learn from them, and in that regard, I can freely learn from them and work better."* *"When working with others, I encourage others and try to solve problem so that we can learn from each other."* And they said they improve on their customer care/customer

retention so that they can share what they know *"Sometime I share certain things, but not things in relation to finances". "I share ideas even with customers. This helps me in the sense that most of my customers like coming back to me from time to time"*

F. How does collaborative problem solving ability influence the skills development of workers with hearing impairment?

Responses revealed that, collaborative problem solving ability, help workers with hearing impairment to be duty conscious and stay focused to their job as quoted *"Because I have certain information that I need to share with others, I come to work every day" "I feel comfortable to go to work every day because I can tolerate others" "I ignore bad behaviour, let go of it, when angry with others and stay focused" "When you understand other people, you feel comfortable around them and so you stay focus in you work."* They further explained that, collaborative problem solving ability encourages them to learn from others, be job effective and retain their job.

G. What workers with hearing impairment do, in order to tolerate others when working with them?

Results revealed that persons with hearing impairment turn to understand others point of view: *"It is generally not easy, to understand people from their own point of view, but I try to understand them.* In order to tolerate others, workers with hearing impairment turn to be patient as seen in these quotations; *"To understand others, I try to be patient" "I try to be patient and pay attention to them." "I am patient so that people can explain themselves to me. I show them love, so that they will tell me the truth" and to stay focused "When communicating or working with friends and customers, I pay a lot of attention, I try not to lose focus, because I do so, I will miss out."*

H. How does the ability to be tolerant, influence the ability to gain new knowledge at work for workers with hearing impairment?

In responding to the above, workers with hearing impairment stated that, this make them to be patients, that is to wait patiently for things to unfold naturally, and to be easy-going as expressed in these quotations: *"When people change their behaviour towards me, I do not get angry, so I can always work with them."* It equally help reduce their anger as revealed by 40% of them as follows *"it help me not to get angry" "Understanding help me to gain new knowledge because I don't get angry"*

They continued by expressing that, this help them to develop new skills as seen in these quotations: *"When working with colleagues work understand me, we share a lot of things." "Understanding others help me not to be angry with them and improve our working relationship." "When I try to understand other people, I develop new skills from them"*. Adding to the above, this help them to be open to their colleagues

I. How workers with hearing impairment manage changes at work?

Findings proved that, to be able to manage changes at work, Workers with hearing impairment, tend to be empathetic The above is summarised in the conceptual diagram below

and curious as quoted by them: *"To manage change, I try not to be selfish, but understand other people's point of view." "I look at situations from their own point of view." "I ask a lot of questions to understand why certain changes are made." "When working with other people, I ask a lot of questions in order to learn" "I am vigilant and look at what they are doing in order to learn" "I pay attention to what my madam is doing, in order not to miss out" "I learn a lot from others by observation"*

They further revealed that to manage change, they try to understand themselves and develop self-confidence *"I try to first of all understand myself." "Knowing whom I am, makes me not to bother about certain things". "I do not get angry with certain things because I know whom I am." "Working with others makes me feel proud about myself, because others are learning from me" "when I am confident of myself, I am not bothered by certain things." "I hold on to myself in the face of changes, because I know who I am."*

J. The influence of workers with hearing impairment's ability to manage changes at work on their skills development?

In responding to this, workers with hearing impairment revealed that, their ability to manage changes at work, improves on their skills development by helping them to be flexible and to develop self-pride as seen in these quotations: *"Because I am flexible to change, I can learn easily" "working with others make me feel proud about myself, because others are learning from me."* They further expressed that, their ability to manage changes at work, help them to be efficient, work collaboratively with others and develop an internal locus of control as quoted: *"I work very hard, because I understand changes". "Because I am not border by certain changes at work, I can work very well with my colleagues and learn from them". "I do not wait for others to do certain things for me."*

To summarise, the findings revealed that, collaboration competencies has a positive impact on the career development of workers with hearing impairment in Fako Division South West Region of Cameroon, as the workers with hearing impairment exhibited certain characteristics which proved that they possess collaboration competencies. Such characteristics were: flexibility, sociable, enjoy working together, collaborative working relationship, tolerant, demonstrative behaviour, the ability to understand others, the ability to be patient, to be empathetic, to be curious, the ability to manage change and the ability to understand oneself. Contrary to the above positive behaviour, workers with hearing impairment also see themselves as victims of gossip and 'Deaf culture.

The negative behaviour notwithstanding, the positive qualities of collaboration competencies possess by workers with hearing impairment, help them to develop a collaborative working relationship, develop a competitive spirit, work very hard, be duty conscious, be job focused, job effective, gain environmental motivation, encourages them to learn from others, retain their job, be patients, develop new skills and to develop self-pride. All these are qualities which positively influence their career development process.

Figure1: Summary diagram depicting the influence of collaborative competencies on the career development of persons with hearing impairment

Colleagues’ Perspectives on the Influence of Collaboration Competencies on the Career Development of Persons with Hearing Impairment

A. How colleagues appreciate the working relationship of the workers with hearing impairment

Colleagues expressed that, workers with hearing impairment sometime express an outburst of emotions when they are angry (temper tantrums). This can make the working relationship very challenging as expressed in these quotations: *“She has a very high temper. When she gets angry, it may be very difficult to relate with her.”* *“Her temper is a challenge, because when she is angry, she will isolate herself and will not want to relate with others.”* They further explained that; these workers with hearing impairment are reflective to situations that, they are emotionally very sensitive.

The colleagues added that, in spite of the uncontrollable outburst of emotions, workers with hearing impairment are friendly as expressed in these quotations; *“But apart from this anger, she is a very nice person to work with.”* *“He has so much concern for others and is very welcoming.”* *“She is very caring and likes to make others people happy”* *“She enjoys a happy environment and shows much love to people who show her love.”* And they try to understand others *“She has the ability to understand me from my face. That is, when I am angry, she can read my facial expression and understand me.”* *“He relate with people, depending on their temperament”*

The colleagues went further to state that, these workers with hearing impairment, try to adapt to situations as seen in these expressions: *“There are moments when the customers we have are not understanding at all, but I see her managing to relate with them.”* *“Sometimes I notice he is uncomfortable, when other colleagues are discussing and he cannot partake in the discussion, but he tries to stay focused”.*

B. The opinion of colleagues of workers with hearing impairment on how the ability to collaborate with others influence their skills development

In responding to the above, colleagues of workers with hearing impairment expressed that, the working relationship of workers with hearing impairment, help them to increase their interpersonal ability as stated by them; *“She can ask questions without fear”* *“In short she love it when you ask her question.”* This also make them to pay attention in their job places, and be hard working as quoted: *“Because we are working together, it is easy for him to focus on certain very important things in the workshop.”* *“She does a lot of observation and develop her own sense of creativity.”* *“She is a senior person in the workshop and does a lot to teach the younger colleague”* They continued by stating that, this behaviour increase their creativity and make them work better.

To add, the colleagues further opined that, the collaborative working relationship of workers with hearing impairment, improves on the communication strategies as expressed in these excerpts: *“His working relation with others help him to overcome his communication challenges”.* *“Also improves their self-confidence”* *“I enjoy her self-confidence and her display of what she knows”* *“the way we relate in the workshop makes him to know that he too has something to share.”* *“His working relationship make work with conviction, because he knows that he will be guided by other colleagues ifhe is going astray.”* and the awareness of their strength *“Working with others make him know that he has certain things to share”* *“His work relation with others help him to overcome his communication challenges and focus on strengths”*

In summary colleagues opined that, workers with hearing impairment possess collaboration competencies such as; being friendly, the ability to understand others, change management skills and the ability to be caring. These positive qualities facilitates their career development by helping them to improve on their interpersonal relationship, pay attention to details, be creative, be hard working, improve on self-confidence, improve on their work performance and improve on their communication strategies. All these are summarised in the conceptual diagram below.

Figure2: Conceptual diagram depicting the opinion of colleagues of persons with hearing impairment on how collaboration influences their skills development

9. Discussion of Findings

How do collaboration competencies influence the career development of workers with hearing impairment in Fako Division, South West of Region Cameroon?

The outcomes of this study exposed that workers with hearing impairment possess characteristics of collaboration competencies. These characteristics were seen in their: being flexible, sociable, having a collaborative skill development spirit, having a competitive spirit, being hardworking, tolerant, having problem solving ability, having demonstrative behaviour, being empathetic, having a collaborative working relationship with others, being patience, being focus and having team spirit. Their possession of these qualities, were further supported by the opinion of their colleagues, who exposed that, persons with hearing impairment were; friendly, understanding others and have change management skills. These qualities fall in line with the characteristics of collaboration competencies as stated by Keast & Mandell (2013) who listed the characteristics of collaboration competencies as such; the ability to read interactions and exchanges, to be trustworthy, have a sense of humour, have empathy (step in shoes), be flexible, be patience, perseverance, commitment, have a cooperative spirit, have strategic relationship building skills, group process skills, change management skills, negotiation skills and many others.

The study further revealed that, collaboration competencies improved on the career development of workers with hearing impairment by reducing their anger, make them stay focus in their jobs and be hard working. This can be supported by the work of Beyond (2018), who expressed that, a good collaborators need to be able to work well with others and conduct themselves in a way that adds value to the socially shared work task.

Findings further revealed that, collaboration competencies help workers with hearing impairment to improve on their career development, by facilitating learning through observation. Findings expressed that, by observing what others are doing and the implication of the observable behaviour in the workshop and the society, workers with hearing impairment tend to perform better in their career. This is in relation to Bandura (1986) who explained that, people learn through observing others' behaviour, attitudes, and outcomes of those behaviours.

Finally, the outcomes of the findings showed that, collaborative competencies guide workers with hearing impairment and improve on their career development, by increasing their interpersonal ability, help them pay attention to details, make them to be curious, make them to be hardworking, improve their self-confidence, improve on their work performance, improve on their communication strategy, increased the awareness of their strength, facilitate their ability to learn, improve on their job effectiveness and retain their job.

10. Implications for Education and Contribution to Psychological Knowledge

From the findings of this study, it is glaring that collaboration competencies play a tremendous role in improving the career development of workers with hearing impairment, by bringing out from them certain qualities which encourages workers with hearing impairment to develop a collaborative working relationship, develop a

competitive spirit, work very hard, be duty conscious, be job focused, job effective, gain environmental motivation, encourages them to learn from others, retain their job, be patients, improve on their interpersonal relationship, help them pay attention to details, be creative develop new skills and to develop self-pride. All these are qualities which positively influence their career development process.

Therefore, in the face of complex challenges face by workers with hearing impairment in the strive to cope with globalisation and the changing trends that come along with the sustainable development goals and the need to reduce hunger and poverty, help people be financially independent, socially comfortable and to be a good contributor to nation building, there is need for collaboration competencies to be used in overcoming career development challenges.

References

- [1] Aziz, U. (2019). The challenge of career selection: the future of jobs. Retrieved April 21, 2020, from <https://atlascorps.org/the-challenge-of-career-selection-the-future-of-jobs/>
- [2] Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- [3] BoldLimited. (2019). Career assistance for the deaf and hearing impaired. Retrieved May 4, 2019, from <https://www.hloom.com/blog/career-assistance-deaf-hearing-impaired/>
- [4] Daryanto. E. (2014). Individual Characteristics, job characteristics, and career development: A study on vocational school teachers' satisfaction in Indonesia. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 2014, 2 (8), pp 698-702. DOI: 10.12691/education-2-8-20
- [5] Doyle, A. (2018). Collaboration definition, skills, and examples. Retrieved July 23, 2019, from <G:\Collaboration Definition, Skills, and Examples.html>
- [6] Fox, H. (2010). Neglect of the deaf in Cameroon. Retrieved September 4, 2019, from Cameroonpostline.com/neglect-of-the-deaf-in-Cameroon/
- [7] Hear-it (2007). Hearing loss affects job opportunities. Retrieved April 22, 2020, from <file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/career%20path%20deaf.html>
- [8] Heibutzki .R. (2020). Problems faced by deaf individuals in finding jobs. Retrieved April 21, 2020 from <file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/career%20path%20deaf%202.html>
- [9] Keast, R., & Mandell, M. P. (2013). Collaborative competencies/capabilities. *Australian Research Alliance or Children and Youth (ARACY). Collaboration Evidence Prevention*. Retrieved May 3, 2019 from aracy.org.au
- [10] Levinson, E. M., & Palmer, E. J. (2005). Preparing students with disabilities for school to-work transition and post school life. *Principal Leadership*, 5, 11-15. Retrieved September, 4, 2029 from <http://www.nasponline.org/resources/principals/Transition%20Planning%20WEB.pdf>

- [11] Mohamed. H. T. (2017). Career development. Retrieved April 21, 2020 from <https://fr.slideshare.net/mhtarimbra/career-development-75121372>
- [12] MBASchool (2020). Career development definition, importance & overview. Retrieved April 21, 2020, from <https://www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/human-resources-hr-terms/1779-career-development.html>
- [13] Ray, M., Wallace, L., Mbuagbaw, L., & Cockburn, L. (2017). Functioning and disability in recent research from Cameroon: a narrative synthesis. *The Pan African Medical Journal*. Retrieved September 3, 2019, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5554653/>
- [14] Rise, B. (2018). 6 Skills Needed for Effective Collaboration. Retrieved May 3, 2019 from file:///C:/Local%20Disk/6%20Skills%20Needed%20for%20Effective%20Collaboration%20%E2%80%93%20RISE%20Beyond.html
- [15] Shey, P. F. (2013). Parents' perspectives on the education of children with disabilities in regular schools in Cameroon: Implications for pre-service and in-service training. *African International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*. 4(4), 13-46
- [16] UNESCO (2017). Education for Sustainable Development Goals. *The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization*, 7(7), 978-92-3-100209-0.

